

ODYSSEUS

NEWSLETTER

2 n d I s s u e

SECOND NEWSLETTER

JANUARY 2024

In our second edition of ODYSSEUS Newsletter, we showcase the highlights of the project's progress the last six months. Find out where and how ODYSSEUS was presented and which are the synergies established.

[READ MORE](#)

Learn about the project's most significant news and updates!

<https://odysseusproject.eu/>

[@odysseus_heu](https://twitter.com/odysseus_heu)

[@odysseusproject-heu](https://www.linkedin.com/company/odysseusproject-heu)

Launch of the EUSurvey!

This anonymous survey has been launched during August 2023 and contributes in redefining cross-border travel for citizens everywhere.

Save a backup on your local computer (disable if you are using a public/shared computer)

ODYSSEUS European project is expected to improve border crossing experience for travelers and border authorities' staff, while maintaining security and monitoring of movements across land and sea EU external borders.

Fields marked with * are mandatory. x

Disclaimer x
The European Commission is not responsible for the content of questionnaires created using the EUSurvey service - it remains the sole responsibility of the form creator and manager. The use of EUSurvey service does not imply a recommendation or endorsement, by the European Commission, of the views expressed within them.

Anonymous mode x
The anonymous option has been activated. As a result, your contribution to this survey will be anonymous as the system will not save any personal data such as your IP address.

ODYSSEUS

Unobtrusive Technologies for Secure and Seamless Border Crossing for Travel Facilitation

I accept your Terms
[Consent_Form.pdf](#)

Section 1

* What type of international borders are you crossing frequently? You can choose more than one answers. between 1 and 4 choices
 Land Train Sea None

[READ MORE](#)

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

1st ODYSSEUS virtual meeting

after the summer break

The last day of August 2023, **ODYSSEUS** partners gathered online to discuss the project's progress during the last month and reveal next steps. They reviewed various aspects of the project, including the **status of their tasks** and resolved critical issues.

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media GIFs

The 3 pilots in motion

Seamless Border Crossing

Secure Identity Verification

Vehicle & Luggage Check Without Stopping

ODYSSEUS pilots were depicted in 3 visually appealing gifs that have been used in the project's **social media accounts** to engage the audience regarding the land, water and train border solutions.

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

The ODYSSEUS project's Pilot at Land is moving forward!

During September 2023, the **Rapiscan Systems Car View In Lane (CVIL) RnD demonstrator unit has been put together!** The platform was used to demonstrate occupied imaging as part of the **ODYSSEUS** project real life scenarios to the European Commission.

[READ MORE](#)

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

ODYSSEUS

at the Policy Seminar

SIMAVI, the project coordinator of the **ODYSSEUS** project participated at **Projects to Policy Seminar** held in Brussels, Belgium from 14 to 15 June, 2023. Over 100 people from several projects of general interest participated and guidance was provided to them regarding the **policy-related outputs** in the following areas: results exploitation and dissemination, innovation uptake, societal impact, AI regulations and Ethics Research.

[READ MORE](#)

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

ODYSSEUS at the Workshop

“EU Borders Security: Acting Ahead across Research, Practice and Policy”

On 27 and 28 September 2023 the Ministry of the Interior of the Slovak Republic presented the project at **“EU Borders Security: Acting Ahead across Research, Practice and Policy” workshop organized by MEDEA Project**. The event was held in Madrid, Spain at the ISDEFE premises in a building equipped with the latest technological gears and a sustainable and energy-efficient infrastructure.

[READ MORE](#)

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

ODYSSEUS

at IPA III EU project

Individual measure for EU support against migrant smuggling and human trafficking in WBs for 2023

ODYSSEUS project was presented by the Ministry of Interior of the Slovak Republic within the framework of **IPA III project Western Balkan workshop** on October 4 and 5, 2023 in Sarajevo, Bosnia.

The main focus of this event was to **increase measures** in Western Balkan countries. The audience consisted people from Bulgaria, Hungary, Slovakia, regions that are part of the Western Balkan region.

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

ODYSSEUS Platform

presented in Singapore

RAPISCAN presented the **ODYSSEUS** project in Singapore on October 19 and 20, 2023. The first day featured the **CBRNE team** comprising experts developing proprietary and cutting-edge technologies for **border security operations in Singapore** while on the second the presentation was given to two groups. The **Immigration & Checkpoints Authority (ICA) team** and the **National Environment Agency (NEA)**.

[READ MORE](#)

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

ODYSSEUS

1st Ethics Workshop

by ISIG

On December 4, 2023, the ODYSSEUS project consortium attended **the 1st Ethics Workshop organised by ISIG - Institute of International Sociology of Gorizia, the ethics manager of the project**. The importance of ethical project management was emphasised and the ethical challenges that arise during the execution of the project were discussed. All participants actively joined in two interactive online activities where they were asked to **brainstorm on potential ethical and data protection issues related to the ODYSSEUS operations** and on mitigation measures.

[READ MORE](#)

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

ODYSSEUS

at ASIT

“Actions Against Trafficking in Human Beings”

ODYSSEUS project was discussed by the Ministry of Interior of the Slovak Republic during an event in Bratislava, Slovakia on December 13, 2023 for the project **ASIT**

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

ODYSSEUS at the Horizon Border Security Projects Workshop

by Frontex

The **ODYSSEUS** project proudly participated in **the Horizon Border Security Projects workshop hosted by Frontex** at its headquarters in Warsaw, Poland, on December 14, 2023. SIMAVI highlighted **ODYSSEUS groundbreaking objectives and activities** emphasizing the technical innovations within the project that are poised to facilitate seamless border crossings on land, water, and trains while steadfastly upholding and safeguarding the rights of travelers.

[READ MORE](#)

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

ODYSSEUS article

“Why crossing borders will no longer be an ODYSSEY from 2025”

The screenshot shows a webpage from the magazine 'Știința & Tehnica'. The article title is 'ODYSSEUS - de ce trecerea granițelor nu va mai fi o odisee din 2025'. The main image depicts a truck at a border crossing with overhead signs. The article text includes a quote from the World Economic Forum and data from Eurostat regarding international transport. A subscription form for the magazine is also visible on the right side of the article.

★★★★★ 0 (0)
de Monica Florea și Dana Oniga

Forumul Economic Mondial a estimat că numărul călătoriilor transnaționale va crește cu 50% în următorii ani, raportat înainte de pandemia COVID-19, ducând numărul lor la 1,8 miliarde până în 2030.

Potrivit Eurostat, în 2015 principalele mijloace de transport pentru călătoriile în afara granițelor țării, efectuate de rezidenții UE, erau împărțite astfel: 53% aerian, 31% autovehicule, 6% cu autobuzul, 5% căi navigabile, 4% căi ferate și 1% alte mijloace de transport.

Întârzierile și cozile intervin cel mai adesea atunci când oamenii traversează atât frontierele terestre, cât și maritime, creând o povară suplimentară pentru autoritățile de frontieră și frustrare în rândul cetățenilor.

Numara Divs:
Adresa Divs de email:
Abonează-mă la newsletterul ST

REVISTA ȘTIINȚĂ&TEHNICĂ

An article by SIMAVI is featured in **the Romanian magazine Stiinta & Tehnica** shedding light on the persistent challenges at land and sea borders. Diving into the heart of the matter, **the writers Monica Florea, Project coordinator and Dana Oniga, Project manager of ODYSSEUS** explore the groundbreaking solutions proposed by the project.

[READ MORE](#)

ODYSSEUS at the Synergy Workshop

by I-SEAMORE

The **ODYSSEUS** project participated at the recent **virtual Synergy Workshop held by I-SEAMORE** on January 12, 2024, where it was involved in dynamic discussions with the **sister projects Flexi-cross, Promenade, and BAG-Intel**. In the introductory session, each project unveiled its distinct mission and accomplishments, ODYSSEUS presentation included the project's journey during the past year. Three parallel sessions followed, Technological focus, Communications & Exploitation and Ethics.

[READ MORE](#)

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

FOLLOW ODYSSEUS ON SOCIAL MEDIA

CONSORTIUM

STAY TUNED FOR UPCOMING ACTIVITIES, EVENTS, AND OPPORTUNITIES TO ENGAGE WITH THE PROJECT!

